

1 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 1**

2

3 Supplementary Figure 1. Calibration curves generated to convert $^{410}/_{480}$ ratios into pH_c
4 values. Fluorescence intensities of individual cells were determined using the Nikon inverted
5 (A) and Keyence (B) fluorescence microscopes. A detailed description of the procedure is
6 given in the Materials and Methods section. Mean values and standard deviations were
7 obtained from three biological replicates.

8 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 2**

9

10 Supplementary Figure 2. Average pH_c values of CEN.PK113-7D cells during a shift to acetic
11 acid containing medium. The pH_c values of at least 85 individual cells were determined
12 before (time point 0) and at different time points after a shift to synthetic medium
13 containing 96 mM (black bars) or 120 mM (white bars) acetic acid (pH 4.5). Mean values and
14 standard deviations were obtained from three biological replicates.

15 **SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE 3**

16

17 Supplementary Figure 3. Correlation between the maximal pH_c drop and the duration of the
18 lag phase upon acetic acid stress. Data are shown for 319 individual cells from CEN.PK113-7D
19 exposed to 96 mM acetic acid (pH 4.5).